

METHODS OF USING VIRTUAL STANDS IN TEACHING COMPUTER SUPPLY

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ABSTRACT

*This article describes the methods of using virtual
stands in the teaching of computer science.*

Today, great positive work is being done in higher education institutions on the introduction of information and communication technologies, in particular, the use of multimedia technologies to enrich the content of the education system, the forms and quality of organization.

The introduction of ICT in the educational process of educational institutions is a key factor in increasing the effectiveness of education. Innovative technologies, including modern, advanced ICT, are being introduced in the education system. In the process of education, it is proved in practice that teaching students on the basis of technical means and multimedia technologies helps them to quickly and easily assimilate the knowledge imparted, to keep them clear and well-remembered. In addition, one of the achievements of the educational process is the possibility of creating virtual

stands in the education system. This opportunity will be an important factor in helping students to exchange ideas, develop free and creative thinking, and communicate their ideas accurately and clearly.

Virtual stands are now being used successfully in higher and secondary special education institutions. What is a virtual stand and what is its role in increasing the effectiveness of education? Virtual stand is a practical stand or training workshop, which helps to strengthen the theoretical knowledge of students, to develop the necessary skills in a particular direction through computer programs and technologies. is a limiting ICT tool. Virtual stands allow each student to "teach" their technical background and monitor their knowledge. The problem of wasting time on laboratory work, understanding it

properly, and so on, is eliminated by computer efficiency.

It is especially important to save financial resources. A modern simple CD can hold dozens, sometimes hundreds, of lab work. Now it is not difficult to calculate how cheap such a virtual laboratory stand will cost. In addition, they can be used to provide general education. Having an Internet connection is even better. The introduction of virtual stands in the educational process will ensure a higher quality of the training process than traditional education. This is achieved through the use of automated instructors and test takers, specialized training manuals consisting of systems, test assignments and questions for self-examination, as well as the rapid updating of the methodological framework of the educational process. Today we have a variety of organizational forms of teaching, modern multimedia technologies and a variety of educational opportunities. This, to a certain extent, ensures that the diplomas of specialists from different educational institutions are highly valued.

The use of virtual stands in the educational process not only improves the quality and efficiency of education, reduces costs, but also creates an environmentally friendly, safe and environmentally friendly

environment. With the introduction of virtual stands, a different approach to the content of education is required. Multimedia stands make it easy for students to not only see but also hear any information. The introduction of modern multimedia technologies in the educational process in the field of "Computer Support" allows to achieve the following results in comparison with traditional education:

- enrich tables and pictures with color, sound, animations, hypertext;
- use of interactive web-elements, tests;
- edagog, enriching the theoretical material of the lesson;
- regular updating of information;
 - More individual work with students in the educational process, increasing their interest in the lesson, supporting and developing their knowledge;
 - strengthening interdisciplinary links in the educational process, a comprehensive study of reality;
 - Improving the flexibility, forms and methods of the educational process, the technological base through the introduction of modern ICT tools.

Figure 1. The main window of the virtual stand.

Figure 2. The mirror of the virtual stand.

In short, today multimedia technologies, virtual stands - one of the most promising areas of informatization of the educational process. The introduction of multimedia technologies in the educational process is an important condition for the ideological development of students and the socio-economic development of our society. That is why it is necessary for today's teacher to work tirelessly, to have a wide range of creative

thinking, to use advanced edagogic and multimedia technologies, to have the necessary qualities for their profession. The introduction of modern information technologies in the educational process requires the improvement of software and methodological support, material resources, as well as training of teachers. Multimedia tools are also important in further improving the skills and abilities of teachers.

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